

Scalable Optimization for Wind Farm Control using Coordination Graphs – Supplementary Material

Timothy Verstraeten^{1,2}, Pieter-Jan Daems², Eugenio Bargiacchi¹, Diederik M. Roijers^{1,3},
Pieter J.K. Libin^{1,4}, and Jan Helsen²

¹Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Artificial Intelligence Lab Brussels, Elsene, 1050, Belgium

²Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Acoustics and Vibrations Research Group, Elsene, 1050,
Belgium

³HU University of Applied Sciences Utrecht, Microsystems Technology, Utrecht, 3584CS,
Netherlands

⁴Hasselt University, Data Science Institute, Hasselt, 3500, Belgium

We perform experiments for the all combinations of the following sets of parameters:

- Wind direction: $d \in \{0^\circ, 30^\circ\}$
- Demand: $P_{\text{dem}} \in \{60 \text{ MW}, 70 \text{ MW}, 80 \text{ MW}, 90 \text{ MW}, 100 \text{ MW}\}$
- Number of high-risk turbines: $n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$
- Penalty: $L^w(s^{G(w)}) = \begin{cases} +\infty & \text{if } w \text{ is high-risk and} \\ & P_t^w(s^{G(w)}) \geq 5.2 \text{ MW} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Each experiment is repeated 100 times.

Overall, the results discussed in the main manuscript are representative for all experiments, and sufficiently demonstrate the performance of SPTS compared to the heuristic approach. Nevertheless, we disclose all obtained results in this document.

Appendix A – Learning Curves

A.1 – Demand Error

Figure 1: Demand error for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 2: Demand error for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 3: Demand error for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 4: Demand error for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 5: Demand error for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 6: Demand error for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 7: Demand error for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 8: Demand error for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 9: Demand error for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 10: Demand error for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

A.2 – Penalty

Figure 11: Penalty for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 12: Penalty for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 13: Penalty for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 14: Penalty for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 15: Penalty for $d = 0^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 16: Penalty for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 17: Penalty for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 18: Penalty for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 19: Penalty for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Figure 20: Penalty for $d = 30^\circ$ and $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW. The average trend and standard deviation are plotted.

Appendix B – Best Set-Point Configurations

The best solutions found by SPTS have no penalty. Therefore, we only show the total penalty for the best solutions obtained by the heuristic approach.

Figure 21: Demand error of best solution for $d = 0^\circ$.

Figure 22: Demand error of best solution for $d = 30^\circ$.

Figure 23: Penalty of best solution found by the heuristic approach for $d = 0^\circ$.

Figure 24: Penalty of best solution found by the heuristic approach for $d = 30^\circ$.

Appendix C – Farm-Wide Power Productions

Appendix C.1 – SPTS

Figure 25: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW.

Figure 26: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW.

Figure 27: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW.

Figure 28: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW.

Figure 29: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW.

Figure 30: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW.

Figure 31: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW.

Figure 32: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW.

Figure 33: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW.

Figure 34: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by SPTS for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW.

Appendix C.2 – Heuristic

Figure 35: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW.

Figure 36: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW.

Figure 37: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW.

Figure 38: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW.

Figure 39: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 0^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW.

Figure 40: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 60$ MW.

Figure 41: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 70$ MW.

Figure 42: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 80$ MW.

Figure 43: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 90$ MW.

Figure 44: Average farm-wide power production of the best solution achieved by the heuristic approach for $d = 30^\circ$ and demand $P_{\text{dem}} = 100$ MW.